

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AKANJI****FIRST NAME: ADESOLA****PROGRAM CODE : DGEP****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The steps in essay writing are in the following order

- Write the first draft; define the question and analyze the task; draft a plan; research the topic; organize your ideas, start early.
- Start early; write the first draft; define the question and analyze the task; draft a plan; research the topic; organize your ideas.
- Start early; define the question and analyze the task; draft a plan; research the topic; organize your ideas; write the first draft.¹**
- Define the question and analyze the task; draft a plan; research the topic; organize your ideas; start early; write the first draft.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7-10.

2. Which of the following sentence is correct about Plagiarism:
- Plagiarism is when you take someone else's words and ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and give credit to the author.
 - Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.²²**
 - Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and gives credit to the author of that source of information
 - Plagiarism is not having someone write a paper for you and you then put your name on it and submit to your professor.
3. Which of the following sentences about sources is correct.
- Read secondary sources to learn from other Researchers.³**
 - Secondary sources are original materials that provides you with raw data.
 - Read primary sources to learn from other Researchers.
 - Tertiary sources are firsthand information.
4. Which of the sentences is not correct about Research:
- Researchers must read and evaluate the work of others before they make decisions.
 - Research is a process of systemic inquiry to answer a question that a Researcher wants to solve.
 - Research is answering a question by obtaining information.

² Ibid., 34.

³ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 35-37.

As a true researcher, you do not have to share your findings and conclusions with others.⁴

5. One of these is not a reason to cite your sources:

- To give credit.
- To reassure others about the accuracy of your facts.
- To show readers you are knowledgeable.⁵**
- To help others follow or extend your research.

6. Which of this information is not required in a citation?

- Who is responsible for creating the source
- Who published the source
- When was the source published
- The address of the publisher of the source.⁶**

7. Which of the following is not a source of potential bias in dissertation research?

- Invention bias⁷**
- Experience bias
- Population bias

⁴ Ibid., 19-20.

⁵ Ibid., 139-140.

⁶ Ibid., 140-141.

⁷ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 8-9.

- Finding bias
8. Which of these sentences is not correct in ensuring a successful dissertation?
- Communicate effectively and regularly with your major professor, especially when difficulties arise.
- Avoid attention to details especially in completing a systematic literature review.⁸**
- Set realistic goals with input from the major professor, establishing specific dates for completing your tasks and writing specific sections of the dissertation.
- Visualize submitting the final approved copy of your dissertation to the university and being hooded at graduation.
9. Which is the correct recommended organization of dissertation components?
- Title, Abstract, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgement, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Introduction, Literature review, Methodology, Findings, Discussions, References, Appendices.
- Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgement, Abstract, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Introduction, Literature review, Methodology, Findings, Discussions, References, Appendices.
- Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgement, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Abstract, Introduction,**

⁸ Ibid., 13-15.

Literature review, Methodology, Findings, Discussions, References, Appendices.⁹

- Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgement, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Abstract, Biography, Introduction, Literature review, Methodology, Findings, Discussions, References, Appendices.

10. According to the rule of *Order of Adjectives*, which of the following sentences is correct?

- An amazing red coat.**¹⁰
- A white large loaf.
- A wooden small table.
- A tasty nice soup.

⁹ Ibid., 20.

¹⁰ Ibid., 50.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.